

THE PLACE OF PLANTS IN HUMAN LIFE AND THEIR ROLE IN CLEANING THE ATMOSPHERE

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Abstract

Plants play a very important role in human life, we cannot imagine our life without plants. 90% of the products we consume are obtained from plants, besides, they enrich the atmospheric air with oxygen. It is also a nutritious food for livestock. The heads of the plants are food for birds. Understanding the role of plants in our lives, each of us should contribute to the growth of plants.

Keywords

Plants, air, animal husbandry, agriculture, vegetables, cash crops, cash crops

The place of plants in human life is very important. Since plants make up most of the things that surround us, we should have complete information about plants, because almost 90% of the products we consume are obtained from plants. For example, bread products, fruits and vegetables, wood products, oils, fodder for livestock, farm soaps, additives used in perfumes, in short, thousands of examples can be given.

We can also use plants as a landscape. Also, quality clothes are made from the fiber of some plants. We can use cotton as an example, because cotton has been grown in Uzbekistan since ancient times, exported to foreign countries where the demand for its fiber is very high, and it has had a very good effect on the development of Uzbekistan.

In our farm, livestock and poultry farming require a lot of attention, of course, plants are nutritious food for livestock, and in poultry farming, grains of spiked plants are nutritious food, as it can be seen that we cannot imagine our life without plants. .

As our honorable president said, we should make good use of every inch of our land, we should plant vegetables, fruit trees, ornamental trees, and flowers. . Even if it is little, we can get additional income, at least we can grow products for

ourselves, which in turn will bring profit, savings and benefit to the family. Now, another important issue is that plants play a big role in cleaning the atmosphere for us. They release oxygen from themselves and absorb carbon dioxide. We know that oxygen is essential for humans and animals. The more oxygen there is in our air, the more it is beneficial for our health, for example: mountains or mountain forests are rich in oxygen because of the dense vegetation, we rarely go to mountainous areas or sparsely populated areas. even if we go for a long time, we will notice a good change in our health, so we should contribute to the reproduction of plants, from decorative flowers to fruit trees, in the environment in which we live, that is, in our house, in our neighborhood, in our city. if everyone starts greening from his family, first of all, we are not indifferent to his family and homeland, the ecological condition of our homeland, the health and culture of ourselves and the next generation. Based on the conditions of the city of Bukhara, we should increase the number of ornamental trees and flowers around the roads and in the city. Trees add to the beauty of the city, clean the air and help to cool down in the hot summer season. We are well aware of the salinity of Bukhara's climatic conditions, and we should pay attention to the breeding of plants that are resistant to salt and can quickly adapt. The result would be good if everyone would consciously make a small contribution and make this issue a tradition at home or at the place of work. We would achieve a good result if everyone had knowledge and skills for the good growth and development of plants in their spare time, and if we could attract and interest our youth from a young age, they would definitely spend their free time in vain. , we will make our young people to increase their love for family, motherland, nature and plants, even if they spend useful time on work instead of spending time on the streets due to idleness. Plants not only clean the air, but decorative plants raise the mood of a person and give inspiration to a person to work with pleasure or creativity. We would share and explain the useful aspects of plants to the younger generation and increase their interest. From annual plants to perennial plants, we need to understand that all of them release oxygen and are useful from their roots to their fruits. For example, if there are simple flowers or trees in the house where we live or in our office, if there are a variety of plants, the mood of a person will rise, when a person is in a good mood, the productivity of a person will be high and it will show the height of our culture. This shows how cultured and tasteful and high our ethics and aesthetics are.

Xulosa : So, knowing that plants have a very important place in human life, we should first of all give children the right understanding about plants from a young age, make them feel that we have a great place in our lives, and if we can create

love in their hearts, then we expect in the future. I think we will achieve a result. Children who love nature, for example, never run over the flowers on the side of the road, do not break the branches of the trees. When they go to the market, they find a child carrying one flower.

As they say, there will be a lake, the result will be good if everyone contributes at least one plant.

Preparation of medicinal plants from plants also increases our love for plants. Every person should live the life that is given to us not just, but also very beautifully. For this, the role of plants is very important for a person. How about sweet fruits, various products, home appliances, various perfumes - soaps, cleaning agents for our cleanliness, high-quality wood products for our modern homes are also obtained from plants. There are many others that have not been mentioned. thus, each of us should contribute to the preservation and reproduction of the plants that nature has gifted.

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